
Analysis of the brand image of a tourist destination

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Abstract :

The brand image of a destination can be considered as the fundamental pillar of the tourism image building and can also be taken as its *raison d'être*. This helps the latter to have a certain resilience against risks and unforeseen events that may affect their activities or jeopardize their future.

The purpose of this research work is to analyze the adequacy between the brand image of a destination and its degree of importance for the implementation or even the development of a resilience strategy. It is based on the theoretical analyse via the analysis of the impact of a destination's brand image on the projection of a strategy that will allow destinations to resiliently deal with risks. The main result of the research shows that the brand image of a destination will be one of the essential perimeters in the structure of each organization. This requires destinations to change their marketing strategies towards the principle of loyalty before starting an evasion strategy.

Keywords: Tourism destination branding, fit analysis, resilience strategy.

Introduction:

The notion of resilience of a tourist destination can be defined as the ability of a destination to resurface and absorb the shock and impact of a crisis, risk or unforeseen event. It encompasses a set of steps and devices put in place by the actors in order to, at the same time, strengthen its way of crisis management, and also to propel itself after having suffered damage or a rout due to a natural disaster, a health crisis or security threats that can harm this sector. It is defined in relation to a certain dynamic and/or flexibility between two situations that are both complementary and contradictory in the search for a balance. It constitutes a process of transformation in time of a situation characterized by a dysfunction in another one more profitable to a destination. It refers to an opportunistic mobility (variation) in a socio-economic development perspective. Understanding and analyzing resilience requires the junction of two different, entangled and complex issues. It refers to both a social construct and participation in social achievement (Kouamékan, 2014: 2).

During the last decades, destinations suffer from a poorly detected, analyzed and treated constraint. Speaking on the notion of the brand image of a destination or the brand equity of the destination as what is agreed to the language of marketers.

Destination image is a recent concept in tourism research (Echtner and Ritchie, 1991). Indeed, research on destination image began in the early 1970s. The image that tourists have of tourist destinations is of indisputable importance since it has an influence on the perception of the destination by tourists, on their behavior, on their choice and on their satisfaction with the tourist experience. It is also linked to the competitive and strategic positioning of a tourist destination. As a result, tourism destinations are currently potential tourists, a better understanding of the destination image is considered vital and more than necessary (Kim and Yoon, 2003).

This leads us to the formulation of our research question as follows: "Is a destination's brand image hooked to its resilience or not?"

The methodological framework of this paper is built on a set of principles. The first is related to the epistemological framework followed. In fact, following a connection made between our conception of the research object, of the knowledge that the present research produces and of the methods used, it appears that the best choice would be to draw inspiration from the constructivist movement.

In order to best answer our research question, we opted for a research method that focuses on the theoretical approach, which includes both theories dealing with the concept of resilience and those that translate the notion of the image of a destination on the field.

1- The emergence of the notion of resilience:

The year 2020 has seen the most important revolution that the global tourism sector has experienced throughout its history. The scale of the crisis is such that, for the first time, the entire ecosystem of this sector was impacted: national and international tourism, business tourism and leisure tourism, beach tourism, mass tourism and niche tourism. The tourist offer was faced with complex national and international sanitary measures and regulations to which it had to adapt. Total flight stoppages, travel bans and other restrictive measures, more or less severe, are the different aspects whose impact has hit hard both sending and receiving countries. Thus, as a whole, the tourism sector was to experience considerable changes, which will subsequently require destinations to implement resilience strategies to mitigate the effects of the crisis.

Mohamed Ait Tejan et al (2018) say that the use of the concept of resilience aims to go beyond adapting to the shock, in order to "develop new avenues for growth. Resilience is defined by the ability to bounce back after confronting risks. In this sense, it is wise to differentiate two basic concepts through which specialists and experts try to analyze and explain the impact of a crisis situation: Resilience and Stability. Thus, the notion of resilience refers more to a strategic intelligence parameter than a return to the pre-crisis situation. Understood in this perspective, resilience is a device that allows for intelligent crisis management and shock absorption. It is, therefore, a vector of strategic innovation.

As the only consumer product for which the consumer must travel to consume at the place of production, the sudden interruption of national and international traffic has resulted in a categorical halt to activity.

Over the last few decades, a wide range of research has been carried out on the issue of destination branding and resilience, which has formed the thread and background for our reflections on the theoretical anchoring of our research theme, on its definition, on its application boundaries...

Tableau 1 - Main authors who have dealt with the concept of resilience

Authors	Definition
Fabry and Zeghni (2019)	We have shown that the literature distinguishes four categories of resilience, starting with resilience in the engineering sense and ending with systematic resilience.
Luthe and Wyss (2016), Scott et al (2016), Tsai and Ni (2016)	Resilience moves from a strictly ecological perspective to climate and environmental change and sustainability.
Dahles and Susiloxati (2015)	Resilience also applies to organizations and individual businesses in the tourism sector. It is based on the adaptability and innovation of businesses.
Lew (2014), Dahles and Susilowati (2015)	Tourism resilience is primarily seen as a way to improve sustainability after an ecological or environmental disaster and offers an alternative to sustainable development.
Duan Biggs, C. Michael Hall, Natalie Stoeckl (2015)	To highlight the concept of resilience as a transdisciplinary concept that has been developed in various disciplines and fields (ecology, systems dynamics, materials science, psychology, planning and more recently in tourism).
Sawalha (2014)	The need to develop a resilient and stronger culture in a competitive context where organizations must cope in a constantly changing environment.
Hallegate (2014)	Resilience aims to provide a response to an expected or unexpected shock that is costly in direct and indirect impacts and in asset losses.
Lew (2014)	For tourism destinations, resilience involves a wide range of slow and fast variables. Slow variables that destinations need to anticipate include climate change, changing macroeconomics and demographics, and increasing tourist flows. Fast variables include, for example, changing weather patterns, natural disasters, geopolitical events, terrorism, changes in consumer preferences, and new technologies.
Berkes and Ross (2013)	Socio-ecological resilience focuses on the interactions within a system that escape the need to return to equilibrium. It is the search for the capacity to adapt, learn and innovate in a context of dynamic interactions.
Ma and Hassink (2013)	Destinations are generally quite complex systems that consist of many interdependent products, actors and institutions and their mutual interactions.
Brouder and Eriksson (2013)	Tourist destinations are "badle of many sources of evolutionary change" determined by "multiple levels of agent interaction in the form of labor, firms, networks, technologies and institutions". Tourist destinations are like any complex adaptive system, always in a process of response and anticipation of endogenous and exogenous shocks and stresses that influence their development and that of the actors involved.
Pisano (2012)	Resilience in the engineer's sense, aims at stability and seeks to preserve the status quo, is a way to return and regain an old balance without adaptation.

Source: Realized by us

Despite this interest in the notion of resilience, the lack of practical and useful applications as well as a conceptual framework (Gallarza et al, 2002), particularly in the field of destination management, has also been questioned due to the fact that the concept remains incomplete (Matos et al, 2012). The vagueness surrounding the concept of resilience begins with its very definition.

To that end, and based on these definitions, it can be concluded that the notion of resilience has become the backdrop of an inescapable strategy in the life of any business. Like other economic sectors, tourism plays an essential, sometimes vital, role in the economy of every country. Indeed, it is more and more considered by the stakeholders as a strategic sector that participates as a locomotive of the socio-economic development.

2- The contribution of the concept of the brand image of a tourist destination

The choice of a tourist destination is not part of a routine purchasing process, conditioned by consumption habits or product access/availability parameters (as is the case for consumer products, for example). It is a decision that requires a relatively large amount of prior information research on possible alternatives because it involves many sacrifices (time available for planning, monetary expenses, purchasing/reservation procedures, consumption of vacation days, etc.) for an expected benefit that is often predetermined (emotions, social exchanges, cultural discoveries, memories, etc.). The image of a tourist destination is therefore fundamental to ensure its attractiveness. For example, a person wishing to discover the castles of the Loire Valley in the spring should choose the ones that seem the most adapted to his objectives of visit (and to the people accompanying him) because they are so numerous that it is inconceivable to visit them all (budget and time to be given to the visits) in only one stay. The choice of these destinations would thus be made according to their perceived image (during the information search phase) and in a comparative manner (comparison of alternative choices). In the classical marketing field, a brand image can be defined as the set of associations and impressions that a consumer has in memory about a brand (Keller, 1993, Aaker, 1991). In the field of tourism, a distinction is made between an organic image, one that is induced, and one that is considered to be complex and formed as a result of a tourist stay.

The organic image comes from consumers' access to non-tourist information sources such as newspapers, magazine articles, television reports, films and friends' opinions. Thus, an individual who has never traveled to a destination and never even considered it as a potential tourism choice will still have an image of it.

The induced image comes from the communication of tourism actors (advertising, brochures, guidebooks, travel agency recommendations), and is intended to "sell" the destination and inform the consumer. Exposure to this information can alter the initial organic image established by consumers. This can lead to confusion and a general misunderstanding of the diversity of the destinations' tourism offerings. Finally, after the visitor's stay, he or she modifies the inductive and organic image into a so-called "complex" image (Frochot et al., 2010). There is thus a significant difference between an image formed before visiting a destination and a modified image after this visit. Tourists may subsequently develop a more positive or negative image after their stay. However, this is related to a lack of knowledge that reduces the perception of the extent and diversity of the destination's tourism offer. As a result, tourists will have a simplified image, not incorporating what the destination can really offer; only the stay will help them evaluate it (Frochot et al., 2010).

In terms of tourist destinations, brand image is considered a decisive factor in the choice of a tourist destination (Baloglu and McCleary, 1999). Also, this choice upstream of the purchase process is based on the capacity of the place of visit to generate a positive image, in particular by valorizing, presenting and communicating on the beneficial attributes that can attract the attention and that they are unique of the destination (Gartner, 1989). Thus, when several tourist destinations are in competition, a strong and distinct image will help it to occupy in the minds of tourists a strong positioning, and this is summarized in the marketing strategy of the TOP OF MIND, that it allows the destination to be the number 1 in the thoughts of potential customers, the day the need is detected, the choice falls directly on it. Hunt (1975) was the first to define the brand image of a destination as the impressions of a country held by people who do not live in that country. It is also associated with the sum of beliefs, ideas and impressions that a person holds about a destination (Crompton, 1979).

Tableau 2 - Some definition of destination branding

Authors	Definition
Murphy, Pritchard, & Smith (2000)	Products and experience opportunities combined to form the final experience of the place visited.
Cooper, Fletcher, Gilbert, & Wanhill (1998)	The set of services that can satisfy the needs of tourists. The destination includes demand, transportation, distribution, and marketing.
Seaton & Bennett (1996)	Individuals want to visit another place where they are offered transportation, lodging, food, and entertainment.
Laws (1995)	The tourist destination is the place where people spend their vacations. The three key elements are: the place, the people and the vacation.
Hu & Ritchie (1993)	Like any other consumer product, the tourism destination is the packaging of tourism services. It is composed of a number of multidimensional attributes.
Middleton (1988)	The tourism destination is composed of five components: 1) The natural attractions of a site; 2) Facilities and services; 3) The ease of access to that site; 4) The image built to attract tourists to that site; 5) The total cost of a vacation.

Source : Realized by us

A tourist destination can be defined as a commercialized territory that reflects specific cultural and territorial orientations. During the last decades, the world in general and the economic situation of the countries have known crises, ruptures and turbulences... which has impacted and presents for the tourist companies difficulties to define its target clientele, the identification of the need among their consumers and therefore to determine its marketing approach.

According to these definitions, a destination is perceived by tourists as a set of parameters that provides a memorable and unforgettable experience and also a maximum sensation, it is the individual well-being of the traveler during the trip.

3- The different types of destination branding:

There are different brand images of tourist destinations, the most known are:

3.1- The cognitive image:

The tourist knows the place and judges it according to what he already knows, with a strong simplifying tendency.

3.2- The dream image:

This is an evoked potential that can determine an attraction or a repulsion. This image is built in the imagination of people who only know the destination through the information provided by the tourist office, the press or other media. The visitor can then confront this dream image

during his or her stay in the resort, a confrontation that may or may not confirm the stereotype linked to the resort. To satisfy the visitor's expectations, it is necessary to know the broad outlines of the dream image by using questionnaires or surveys.

3.3- The image that can be identified:

This is a notoriety that can be measured in the tourism literature. It is possible to measure the notoriety of the resort, as well as that of the logo that represents it. The logo is indeed a recognizable element and it is therefore essential to choose a logo that is easily identifiable.

3.4- The desired image :

It can be defined according to the promotional documents that have been supported in the past and that lead to the current image. In this sense, time is an important order of magnitude in tourism communication, a fact that requires an effort in the study of a clear and coherent image policy with that practiced in the past.

3.5- The real image:

It is determined by a classification of the concrete elements of the resort such as natural attractions, accommodation capacity or ease of access (Lanquar and Hollir, 2002)

Tourists visit certain destinations with direct reference to functional associations such as "visit Paris for its Eiffel Tower, its museums", or more abstract ones such as "visit Ibiza as a fashionable destination". These behaviors emanate directly from the associations that the tourist attaches to the destination brand as it is present in his mind. A tourism destination brand has a strategic combination of elements that serve to identify and position it. These elements, similar to a consumer product, can be one or more names, signs, logos, slogans, colors, typography, etc. The destination brand is considered successful when it is able to project a simple, attractive, credible, and distinct image. (Christèle Camelis et al, 2017).

4- Choosing a tourist destination:

Various factors influence the choice of a tourist destination citing at this level:

- The price; The security;
- The natural landscape;
- The diversity of excursions;
- The quality of the cuisine and catering;
- The history of the country and its monuments;
- The quality of the staff, the local culture;
- The ease of access to the destination and the image of the destination.

Therefore, all these factors influence the tourist's choice of a travel destination. The table below summarizes the factors that influence tourist behavior towards a destination:

Tableau 3 - Generic dimensions used by clients to assess quality

Dimensions	Definition	Examples of questions customers may ask
Credibility	Trustworthiness Honesty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the hypermarket near me have a good reputation? - Does my supplier pressure me to buy?
Safety	Absence of danger, risk, doubt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is it dangerous for me to fly with this airline? - Am I sure my computer is properly protected from viruses?
Accessibility	Easy access and easy contact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is it easy to make reservations at my favorite restaurant? - Is the hotel in an easily accessible location?
Communication	Listening to guests, Informing guests regularly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If I have a complaint, is the management willing to listen to me? - Does this specialist use language I understand? - Does the person I'm speaking to let me know when he or she reschedules our appointment?
Understanding the client	Efforts to know the clients and their needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are they listening to me to understand my desires in this company? - Does my banker understand the nature of my financial goals?

Source: Denis Lapert, "Le marketing des services", P 87.

5- Factors influencing tourist behavior

Michel Balfet (2001) proposed three essential factors that explain consumer choices in a profound way:

- Personal, psychological and socio-cultural elements;
- The situational elements and those related to time and place;
- Elements linked to the marketing action of the system offering the service.

Bibliography:

- (1) Understanding consumer practices in the face of the charter of life [Review] / aut. Gaelle Pothin Hajer Bachouche, Christèle Camelis, Ouidade Sabri // Marketing Research and Applications. - 2017.
- (2) The Measurement of Destination Image : An Empirical Assessment [Review] / aut. Charlotte M. Echtner J.R. Brent Ritchie // Journal of Travel Research. - 1993.
- (3) Co-construction of the tourism experience: tourists' strategies in winter sports resorts [Review] / aut. Dominique Kreziak Isabelle Frochot // ProQuest Journal. - 2011.
- (4) Motivations for pleasure vacation [Review] / aut. Crompton John L. // Annals of Tourism Research . - 1979.
- (5) Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Managing Customer- Based Brand Equity [Review] / aut. Keller Kevin Lane // The Journal of Marketing . - 1993.
- (6) Destination image : Towards a Concepal Framework [Review] / aut. Martina G. Gallarza Irene GilSaura, Haydée Calderón García // Annals of Tourism Research. - 2002.
- (7) Crises, learning and resilience: a retrospective analysis of tourism activity in Morocco from 1991 to 2016. Zooming in on the destination Marrakech [Review] / aut. Mohamed Ait Tejan Larbi Safaa // OpenEdition Journals. - 2018.
- (8) Revisiting the destination image construct throught a conceptual model [Review] / aut. Nelson Matos Jùlio Mendes, Patricia Pinto // Tourism, Hospitality & Management Journal (DATHMJ). - 2012.
- (9) Tourism marketing [Book] / aut. Robert Lanquar Robert Hollier. - [s.l.] : PUF, 15/09/2002.
- (10) The hierarchical Effects of Affective and Cognitive Components on Tourism Destination Image [Review] / aut. Seehyung Kim Yooshik Yoon // Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing . - 2008.

(11) A model of destination image formation [Review] / aut. SeyhmusBaloglu Ken W.McCleary // Annals of Tourism Research. - 1999.

(12) Tourism Image: Attribute Measurement of State Tourism Products Using Multidimensional Scaling Techniques [Review] / aut. Gartner William C. // Journal of Travel Research. - 1989.

(13) Territorial resources and tourist destinations: couples in the making? [Review] / aut. Pierre-Antoine Landel Laurent Gagnol and Mari Oiry-Varacca. - 2014. - Journal of Alpine Research | Journal of Alpine Geography : Vol. 102-1.

(14) Territorial resilience as a factor in the emergence of a sustainable tourism destination. Case of the Taksebt dam (Tizi-Ouzou, Algeria) [Review] / aut. Abrika Amina Smadi and Bélaïd // Open Edition Journals. - 2018.

(15) Resilience and tourism: from a cyclical crisis to a structural transformation [Review] / aut. Masclanis François // Téoros ; Journal of tourism research. - 2020.

(16) Image as factor in Tourism Development [Review] / aut. D.Hunt John // Journal of Travel Research. - 1975.

(17) Resilience and societies: concepts and applications [Review] / aut. J.M.K Kouamékan // Ethics and Economics. - 2014.